

Collective or Individual? Tourists' travel mode choice during a pandemic

Vu Thi Thao^{*}, Andreas Philippe Hüsler, Timo Ohnmacht

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts – School of Business, Competence Center for Mobility, Rösslimatte 48, P.O. Box 2960, CH-6002 Lucerne, Switzerland

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Travel mode choice
Health belief model
COVID-19
Holiday journeys
NPIs
Tourist destination

ABSTRACT

The coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) led to holiday journeys being associated with significant health risks. While there are numerous studies on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on travel mode choice in everyday mobility, there are a lack of studies on tourists' choice of travel mode, even though tourism transport in Switzerland makes up 24% of all distance travelled. Based on an extended conceptual framework of the Health Belief Model (HBM), this study investigates the effect of COVID-19 on tourists' intentions to choose a particular travel mode during the pandemic. Our findings show that the higher the perceived susceptibility of getting COVID-19 associated with the holiday journey, the lower the choices for collective travel modes. Furthermore, for those tourists who are more likely to take risks, their choices for collective travel modes are increased. The study recommends that public transport operators choose measures that increase the application of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) against pandemics while travelling; this may encourage the safe use of collective transport modes during a pandemic.

1. Introduction

Travel restrictions brought in place to stop the spread of the virus during the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19) had a tremendous impact on the transport (Benita, 2021) and tourism sector worldwide (WTTC, 2022). For example, in Switzerland in March 2020, in response to the rapid increase of COVID-19 cases, the Swiss Federal Council imposed a 'lockdown light' for an 'extraordinary situation' and used its Epidemics Act to reduce the spread of the virus. The council ordered the temporary closure of shops, restaurants, entertainment and recreational facilities, as well as closing its borders with neighbouring countries for purely leisure purposes. Unlike other countries, Switzerland did not implement a complete lockdown during the COVID-19 pandemic; essential services such as supermarkets and chemists, transportation and hotels, remained open (The Federal Council, 2020). This special context provides an insight for research on policy interventions, such as how the health risk perceptions of the public influenced their choice of travel modes for holiday journeys during a global pandemic.

Numerous studies have investigated the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on travel behaviour patterns and travel mode choice in everyday mobility (Abdullah et al., 2021, 2020; Airak et al., 2023; Anwari et al., 2021; Hintermann et al., 2023; Paul et al., 2022; Politis et al., 2021; Sträuli et al., 2022), and transport response measures (Benita, 2021; Peralvo et al., 2022). Some of them (Aaditya and Rahul,

2021; Anwari et al., 2021; Dingil and Esztergár-Kiss, 2021; Eisenmann et al., 2021; UNWTO, 2020) also include travel for recreational purposes in their studies, but holiday travel is not their main focus. Another research area addresses the effects of the pandemic on tourists' travel intentions during the pandemic (e.g., Abraham et al., 2021; Golets et al., 2021; Nambulee et al., 2023; Neuburger and Egger, 2021; Pappas, 2021; Thao et al., 2022). To the best of our knowledge, no existing studies examine the influence of the COVID-19 pandemic on tourists' intentions to choose travel modes to tourist destinations.

In this context, perceptions of health risks are considered as an important component in understanding behavioural changes in travelling (Kim et al., 2021). Previous studies revealed that during the COVID-19 pandemic, daily changes in travel behaviour were a response strategy to reduce the risks of contracting or spreading the virus (Benita, 2021), which travellers perceived would be a major threat to the health of themselves and the wider public (Shahin and Hussien, 2020). This may involve travel avoidance (Shamshiripour et al., 2020), preferences for traveling by private car or non-motorised vehicles, in preference to collective passenger transport (Scorrano and Danielis, 2021; Zafri et al., 2022), or the application of non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) while using public transport (Kamenidou et al., 2020). Some authors examine the correlation between the perceptions of the risk of contracting coronavirus associated with different modes of transport and travel mode choices (Barbieri et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021; Zafri et al.,

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: thaothi.vu@hslu.ch (V.T. Thao).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2024.101150>

Received 21 November 2023; Received in revised form 11 June 2024; Accepted 19 June 2024

Available online 7 July 2024

2590-1982/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2022), while others attempt to quantify the perceptions of risk when using various transport modes (Kadali et al., 2022; Ozbilen et al., 2021).

Within this research stream, the Health Belief Model (HBM) serves as a widespread theory in health behaviour research (Champion and Skinner, 2008). It proposes that health-related behaviour depends on the perceived susceptibility and severity of a health threat, as well as the perceived benefits and barriers to adopting a health measure to reduce the likelihood of catching the disease, or to decrease the harshness of its consequences (Rosenstock, 1974). In tourism, it has been applied in predicting travel intentions and tourists' protective behaviour during the pandemic (Bae and Chang, 2021; Chua et al., 2021; Hüsser et al., 2023; Thao et al., 2022). However, this model has not been adopted in explaining travel mode choice in a global pandemic in the tourism domain.

This study aims to fill these gaps by investigating the predictors of tourists' intentions during the COVID-19 pandemic in choosing either an individual or a collective mode of transport to travel to a tourist destination with at least one overnight stay. For the data analysis, a subset of 748 Swiss people from a representative survey conducted in 2021 was used. We apply the HBM conceptual framework to examine the influence of the perceived susceptibility and severity of contracting the virus while travelling, as well as the perceived barriers to complying with NPIs against COVID-19 when choosing either of these travel modes. The Domain-Specific Risk-Taking Scale (DOSPERT) in the recreational domain will be also used as one of the predictors (Weber et al., 2002). This scale has been adopted in sociopsychological studies to measure the risk attitudes and behaviour of individuals based on an assessment of the benefits and consequences of engaging in an activity. Hence, our study expands the discussion of how health-risk perceptions influence choices of travel mode by determining the elements (susceptibility or severity) of risk perceptions and protective behaviour responses during a pandemic. These aspects have not been addressed in previous studies in the tourism domain, even though tourism transport in Switzerland makes up 24 % of all distance travelled (Ohnmacht and Balthasar, 2023).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. First, we examine the literature on risk perceptions regarding different travel modes and changes in travel mode choice during the COVID-19 pandemic. The survey, measures, and data-preparation process, are described before turning to the presentation of descriptive statistics, followed by the binary logistic regression results on tourists' intentions to choose either the collective or individual travel mode. In conclusion, we discuss the implications for management of promoting the use of the collective travel modes (i.e., public transport and aeroplanes) while, with the aid of NPIs, ensuring safe travel to reduce tourists' perceived health risks associated with these modes of transport.

2. Literature review

2.1. Risk perceptions of different travel modes during the COVID-19 pandemic

Empirical studies of public risk perceptions associated with a highly contagious virus such as the SARS-CoV-2 in 2019 report that the public's risk perceptions are influenced by a combination of factors, ranging from personal to external factors such as health status or watching how the pandemic develops (Cipolletta et al., 2022). Among sociodemographic and socioeconomic factors, gender (Dryhurst et al., 2020), age (Germani et al., 2020), and income (He et al., 2021) are found to influence risk perceptions of contracting COVID-19 significantly. These studies found that those who were female or young adults, or who had lower incomes, perceive higher risks than those who are male or older adults, and/or have higher incomes. Family situations, such as having children or living within clinically vulnerable, high risk groups, also increase the perceived risk (He et al., 2021). Personal factors such as exposure to social media (He et al., 2021) and direct experiences with

the virus (Dryhurst et al., 2020) can affect the perceived risk as well. Previous studies also observe the role of socio-psychological factors in perceived risks to health; for instance, trust in the government (Wang et al., 2022) and in science (Dryhurst et al., 2020) reduce the perceived risks of coronavirus.

Reviewing literature on the correlation of transport modes and the spread of the coronavirus, Muley et al. (2020) have called for research on travellers' perceptions of the risk of different travel modes during COVID-19. So far, four studies have been devoted to this topic, two of which focus solely on collective transport, while the other two look at different travel modes. In South Korea, Kim et al. (2021) found that people perceived the risk of travelling via the underground the highest risk, followed by trains and buses. Changes in personal factors (emotions, health, daily life, and physical activity) because of COVID-19 have positive impacts on the perceived risk of public transport (bus, tram, train and the underground), while attitudinal changes in compliance with various measures of social distancing have no such influence. The perceived risks of indoor and outdoor public spaces positively influence individuals' perceptions of the risks of public transport.

Rahimi et al. (2021) carried out a survey in the USA and found that ethnicity (being African American) and working in transportation services were associated with perceptions of a lower risk of using buses, while females and those with lower incomes perceived a higher risk of using this mode of transport. The perceived risk of using ridesharing services is positively associated with females, senior citizens and living with grandparents. Built environment settings, such as transportation network densities and living in transit-oriented areas, also have an influence on the perceived risk of using buses and ridesharing. Those who used the bus frequently before the pandemic perceived using the bus during the pandemic as a lower risk.

Zafri et al.'s (2022) study, conducted in Bangladesh, shows that individuals perceived the risk of public transport highest, followed by shared mobility on-demand, and then private travel modes. They explained this with reference to the great difficulty of social distancing on public transport. Like Rahimi et al. (2021), they also found that perceived risks of travel modes depend on gender, age and income. Concerns about the negative health consequences of the COVID-19 infection, and trust in preventative measures against the virus, also influenced the perceived risks of travel modes.

During the pandemic, Ozbilen et al. (2021) conducted a survey in the USA and reported that the risk of COVID-19 infection was perceived more highly in relation to public transport, ride-hailing and car-sharing than in private cars and walking. They also found a different risk perception among transport users and different ethnic groups. Compared with transit users and shared mode users, car users perceived shared mobility-on-demand riskier with regards to catching coronavirus than in private cars.

These studies provide first insights into the perceived risks associated with different travel modes in everyday life. However, the perceived risks of different travel modes for recreational purposes, especially when undertaking holiday journeys, remain under-researched. Thus, there is a need to understand how tourists perceive the health risks of different travel modes and how these risk perceptions influence their intentions to choose travel modes for their trips.

2.2. Changes in travel mode choice during the COVID-19 pandemic

Reviewing studies published in 2020 and 2021 on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on travel behaviour, Paul et al. (2022) found that public transport is by far the least preferred mode of travel, followed by ride-hailing and ride-sharing services, whereas walking, cycling, and using private vehicles are among the most preferred modes of transportation. To illustrate this in more detail, Scorrano and Danielis (2021), for instance, used three different statistical models to estimate determinants of mode choice as a robustness check. All their models confirmed that busses were the least popular modes of travel and

walking the preferred choice.

Traffic data also shows significant changes in mode choices during the pandemic. Travelling by public transport suffered the largest decrease, whereas travelling by private car and cycling experienced the greatest increase (Aloi et al., 2020; Jenelius and Cebecauer, 2020; Molloy et al., 2021). Governmental protective measures, and personal decisions, are considered the main causes of the fall in public transport use (Jenelius and Cebecauer, 2020). In Switzerland, journey numbers and daily distances travelled on public transport were reduced by 50 % and 90 % respectively, compared to before the pandemic. This change is a consequence of the COVID-19 crisis, the lockdown, and work-from-home measures (Hintermann et al., 2023).

In sum, perceived risks associated with different modes of transport are therefore considered an important factor influencing individuals' decisions in their choice of travel modes during the pandemic. A high risk perception is considered a major cause of the reduced use of public transport (Kim et al., 2021).

3. Data and methods

3.1. Data

This study used a subset of data extracted from a representative cross-sectional survey of the Swiss population carried out between 9 March and 18 May 2021. A total of 4,530 people living in Switzerland aged 18 years and above were randomly invited by mail to participate in the survey. The sample was taken from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office and included the linguistic region (German, French, Italian) and gender as strata. Participants had a choice of answering the questionnaire either online or by paper method which they could return using a prepaid envelope. Reminders were sent three weeks after the initial contact. In total, we received 1,683 complete questionnaires, equivalent to a response rate of 39 %. The survey was about the impact of the coronavirus pandemic on individual travel behaviour with respect to a holiday journey, and preventative measures against the spread of COVID-19 and contact with it. It consisted of several topics.

For the purposes of this study, in our analysis we only included respondents who planned to travel on holiday with at least one overnight stay during the pandemic. Of the total 1,683 respondents, 793 stated that they had planned a trip during the pandemic in 2021. Of the remaining 793 respondents, 45 were excluded from the analysis because

they selected the "other" category for the mode of transportation before and/or during the pandemic. This category included modes of transport that were not clearly classifiable as either public or private (e.g., cable car, ski lift, or ferry). Thus, a total sample of 745 respondents remained for the analysis. The respondents were asked about their perception of the risks of contracting COVID-19 on public transport, in private cars, on aeroplanes, and walking in public spaces; to assess the susceptibility and severity of contracting COVID-19, as well as the barriers of applying NPIs while travelling; the travel mode they intended to use for the longest distance in getting to their planned destination; and the travel mode they had used for the longest distance in getting to their tourist/holiday destination before the pandemic.

Table 1 shows the demographic and risk-related characteristics of our subsample. Compared with the Swiss census (FSO, 2021a, 2021b), our sample has a similar distribution of gender, but the respondents are slightly older and have a higher level of education. For the risk-related characteristics, most of the respondents did not belong to a risk group, but slightly over half of them had contact with this group. Nearly half the respondents had taken a coronavirus test, of whom only 10 % turned out positive. Approximately 90 % knew someone directly who had been infected with the coronavirus. Nearly a third of the respondents were in quarantine or isolation.

3.2. Measures and data preparation

Each of the four variables of HBM was measured with relevant items based on previous studies (e.g., Jonas et al., 2011; Rosenstock, 1974) and adapted to the purpose of the present study. A five-point Likert scale was used for rating these items in the survey (e.g., 1: disagree strongly, 5: agree strongly). Two pretests with 300 individuals each were carried out to test the reliability and validity of the scales. We removed a few items for reasons of redundancy. We ended up with three items for risk-taking behaviour during leisure time and four items for the other theoretical constructs.

Risk-taking behaviour in recreational time was measured using three items (e.g., "Would you stay in a tent out in the wild, remote from any towns or campsite.?"?) using five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 = very unlikely to 5 = very likely. The perceived susceptibility of catching COVID-19 when travelling was measured using four items (e.g., "It's likely that I will be exposed to the coronavirus when travelling at this time.") on five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 = "do not agree at all"

Table 1
Demographic and risk-related characteristics.

Gender	Male	Sample (%)	Swiss census (%)
	Female	50	50
Age	18–30	12	19
	31–55	43	44
	56–65	22	16
	65+	23	21
Education	Compulsory and vocational training	37	46
	Grammar school	8	9
	Higher education	23	15
	Tertiary education	32	30
Risk group (by self-declaration)	Yes	26	–
	No	74	–
Contact with risk group	Yes	58	–
	No	42	–
COVID-19 test	Yes	46	–
	No	54	–
Positive test	Yes	10	–
	No	90	–
Someone in close environment has been tested positive	Yes	88	–
	No	12	–
Has been in quarantine or isolation	Yes	26	–
	No	74	–

n = 748.

to 5 = “fully agree”. The perceived severity of COVID-19 was measured using four items (e.g., “Getting infected with the coronavirus would have severe consequences for my physical health.”) on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = “do not agree at all” to 5 = “fully agree”. Finally, perceptions of the barriers of NPIs while travelling were measured with four items (e.g., “The protective measures are disturbing when travelling.”) on five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 = “do not agree at all” to 5 = “fully agree”.

The perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 for different travel modes were each measured using a single item on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = “very low” to 5 = “very high”. To reduce model complexity, we only included the variable perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 on public transport and the variable perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 in private cars. They can represent the perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 in the collective and private travel modes respectively.

Whether the respondents belong to the risk group, had already been tested for coronavirus, whether the test was positive, whether the respondents have ever had to be quarantined or isolated, whether they have had contact with at-risk persons in the same household, or whether they know someone in their close environment who has already been infected with coronavirus was dichotomised with simple yes (1) / no (0) items (see Table 1 for shares).

The means, standard deviations, Cronbachs’ alpha, Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for the latent constructs can be found in Table 3.

To examine the factorial validity of the latent constructs, we adopt the principal axis factoring (PAF) method for an exploratory factor analysis (EFA). We use a Promax rotation ($\kappa = 4$) with Kaiser-Normalization to take into account possible correlations between the latent constructs (Weiber and Mühlfeld, 2014). The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy (Kaiser, 1974) is 0.804, indicating that the items are very well suited for factorial analysis. Bartlett’s test of Sphericity (Bartlett, 1950) was significant ($\chi^2(105, N = 744) = 5541.0, p < 0.001$), statistically rejecting the hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix.

The correlations between the constructs are depicted in Table 2. The Cronbach’s alpha coefficients for all five factors are higher than the 0.70 threshold (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994), suggesting that the constructs have a high level of internal consistency. The Composite Reliability for all constructs is higher than the required 0.70 threshold (Hair et al., 2017). The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for convergent and discriminant validity is greater than the critical threshold of 0.50 for all constructs as well (Fornell & Larcker, 1981) (see Table 3). The four constructs can explain 60.4 % of the variance. The mean indices value for each construct was computed after performing the factorial validity and reliability analysis.

Drawn on the above literature review, we consider that shared modes of transport are perceived as presenting a higher risk of contracting COVID-19 than individual, private modes of transport. We therefore divide respondents into two modal groups based on the travel modes they intended to use for the longest distance to their planned

Table 2
Correlation between the theoretical constructs.

Construct	Risk-taking behaviour	Perceived susceptibility	Perceived severity	Perceived barriers
Risk-taking behaviour	1			
Perceived susceptibility	-0.171**	1		
Perceived severity	-0.281**	0.357**	1	
Perceived barriers	0.158**	-0.097**	-0.242**	1

Note. ** $p < 0.01$, two-tailed (listwise).

Table 3
Principal axis analysis (promax = 4).

	Loading	M (SD)	Alpha	CR	AVE	n
Risk-taking behaviour		2.07 (1.12)	0.753	0.758	0.512	746
Would you stay in a tent out in the wild, remote from any town or campsite?	0.654					
Would you join a white-water rafting tour in fast-flowing rivers in the spring?	0.809					
Would you do risky sports (e.g., rock climbing, skydiving, etc.) regularly?	0.719					
Perceived susceptibility of getting COVID-19 while travelling		3.14 (1.03)	0.877	0.888	0.666	742
It’s likely that I will be exposed to the coronavirus when travelling at this time.	0.599					
There is currently a high risk of infection from the coronavirus when travelling.	0.875					
There is currently a high risk of passing on the coronavirus when travelling.	0.820					
There is currently a high risk of coming into contact with the coronavirus when travelling.	0.930					
Perceived severity of COVID-19		2.99 (1.11)	0.870	0.875	0.634	737
Getting infected with the coronavirus would have severe consequences for my social life (friends, club, sport).	0.662					
Getting infected with the coronavirus would have severe consequences for my physical health.	0.816					
Getting infected with the coronavirus would have severe consequences for my mental well-being.	0.904					
Getting infected with the coronavirus would have severe consequences for my mental ability to perform.	0.786					
Perceived barriers of NPIs while travelling		2.87 (1.08)	0.820	0.781	0.528	743
For me, the costs (time, comfort, money) of applying protective measures when travelling are greater than the benefits.	0.760					
For me, the effort of applying protective measures when travelling is greater than the benefits.	0.808					

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

	Loading	M (SD)	Alpha	CR	AVE	n
The protective measures are disturbing when travelling.	0.655					
The protective measures prevent pleasant travelling.	0.707					

Note. M (SD) = mean (standard deviation), Alpha = Cronbach's Alpha, CR = Composite Reliability, AVE = Average Variance Extracted, n = listwise exclusion.

tourist destination during the pandemic.

The collective transport mode group consists of respondents who planned to use public transport, aeroplanes, and tour buses. This is the target outcome, and we code them as 1. The individual transport mode group consists of respondents who intended to use private cars, cycling or walking. We code them as 0. Table 4 shows that the number of respondents who planned to undertake a holiday by choosing a collective travel mode is lower than those intending to use an individual travel mode. This is in line with what was discussed in the literature review.

To estimate the relationship between the probability of the intention to choose a collective or individual travel mode (outcome variable) and the predictor variables from HBM theory, we carry out a binary logistic regression model in SPSS version 29. Based on the literature review above, we include socio-demographic background factors, the DOSPERT-Scale, risk-related factors, the perceived risks associated with different travel modes, gender, and age in our model.

4. Findings

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Fig. 1 reveals that cars and aeroplanes were the main modes of transport to a tourist destination prior to the pandemic. These travel modes were still the main modes that respondents intended to use for their holidays during the pandemic. However, there was a significant change in mode choices as consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic, as indicated by a Chi-Square Test ($\chi^2(25, N = 748) = 583.124, p < 0.001$). Before the pandemic, aeroplanes (48.7 %) were reported to be the most common travel mode used to get to a destination, followed by cars (38.0 %). The opposite is true during the pandemic: cars accounted for 54.1 % and aeroplanes 30.1 %. Interestingly, tourists tended to compensate for some reduction in travel by aeroplane by going via public transport as well as by car.

In the tourism domain, cycling during the pandemic increased only slightly in comparison to before. This may be explained by the fact that the travel distance for at least one overnight stay at a destination is too far for cycling or walking. In fact, the increase in cycling was, in daily mobility, rather high (Hintermann et al., 2023).

Fig. 2 shows that the perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 was highest in association with public transport, even more so than aeroplanes. This is surprising given the similar social distancing rules applied to these two travel modes. The lowest perceived risk was found to be associated with private cars. Catching COVID-19 while walking in public spaces was also considered as very low risk.

The perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 on public transport (M = 3.70, SD = 1.05) was significantly higher than the perceived risk of

Table 4

Percentage of respondents' intentions choosing travel modes.

Travel mode	n	Percentage (%)
Collective	335	44.8
Individual	413	55.2

n = 748.

Fig. 1. Mode choice for a holiday journey before the pandemic, and intention to use travel modes for a holiday journey during the pandemic.

contracting COVID-19 in a car (M = 1.62, SD = 0.95) ($t(744) = 40.53, p < 0.001$), on aeroplanes ($t(742) = 5.65, p < 0.001$) or walking in public spaces ($t(743) = 48.70, p < 0.001$).

Table 5 provides the characteristics of two tourist groups that are relevant for the regression modelling. The data suggest that the shares of choosing a collective travel mode are higher with younger (18–30) and older (65+) age groups. Gender seems to have no influence on tourists' intention to choose a particular travel mode. Regarding the scales (DOSPERT, HBM), Table 5 shows that the mean values do not change much according to the groups, except the perceived susceptibility is higher for individual travel mode which is, at first sight, counterintuitive. For these results will be statistically controlled for in the modelling section.

4.2. Modelling results of mode choices

We estimated a binary logistic model to examine the influence of health risk perceptions (HBM) on tourists' intentions to choose either a collective or individual travel mode. The Chi-square test of model significance ($X^2 = 65.899, df = 17, p < 0.001$) indicates that the model fits significantly better in predicting the probability of tourists' intentions to choose a collective travel mode, compared with the baseline model (only including an intercept). The Hosmer and Lemeshow test is non-significant ($X^2 = 9.52, df = 8, p = 0.300$), suggesting that the model has a good fit. Cox and Snell's and Nagelkerke's R square are 0.09 and 0.12, respectively. The model correctly predicted 65.9 % of the choices (50.3 % for collective travel mode, and 78.4 % for individual travel mode).

Table 6 presents the results of the binary logit model on the effect of identified variables on the probability of choosing a collective instead of an individual travel mode. The exponentials of coefficients provide changes in the odds ratio of collective to individual travel mode per unit change in the variable. Odds ratios of less than 1 indicate a decrease in the odds of choosing a collective travel mode relative to the odds of choosing an individual one. Odds ratios greater than 1 indicate an increase in the odds of choosing a collective travel mode relative to the odds of choosing an individual travel mode.

Table 6 shows the regression coefficient (changes in the logits), Wald test, odds ratio, and the 95 % confidence interval for the odds ratio. As expected, the perceived susceptibility of contracting COVID-19 while travelling has a negative effect on the probability of choosing the collective in favour to the individual travel mode. For a one-unit increase in the perceived susceptibility, the odds of choosing the collective travel mode over the individual travel mode decrease by 18.7 % ($B = -0.207, p < 0.05, 95\% \text{ CI } 0.687 \text{ to } 0.963$).

Risk-taking behaviour also shows the expected effect on intention to

Fig. 2. Perceived risks of contracting COVID-19 in different travel modes.

Table 5

Characteristics of tourists by intention to choose a travel mode.

	Travel mode choice Individual travel mode (n = 413)	Collective travel mode (n = 335)
Gender (%)		
Female	48.8	50.6
Male	51.2	49.4
Age group (%)		
18–30	11.0	14.0
31–55	45.8	40.4
56–65	23.5	19.5
65+	19.6	26.1
DOSPERT (mean)	1.95	2.22
HBM (mean)		
Perceived susceptibility	3.25	3.00
Perceived severity	3.03	2.95
Perceived barriers NPIs	2.89	2.84

choose the collective travel mode. For a one-unit increase in risk-taking behaviour, the odds of choosing the collective travel mode over the individual mode increase by 27.4 % (B = 0.242, p < 0.01, 95 % CI 1.085 to 1.497). This suggests that during the pandemic, risk-tolerant individuals are more likely to choose a collective travel mode to get to a destination, while risk-averse people are more likely to choose an individual travel

Table 6

Binary logistic model (1 = collective mode vs. 0 = individual mode).

Variable	B	Std.	Wald	Sig.	Odds ratio(Exp(B))	95 % CI LL	UL
Constant	0.507	0.667	0.561	0.454	1.661		
HBM							
Perceived susceptibility	-0.207	0.086	5.732	0.017	0.813	0.687	0.963
Perceived severity	-0.034	0.085	0.157	0.692	0.967	0.818	1.143
Perceived barriers NPIs	-0.084	0.078	1.167	0.280	0.919	0.789	1.071
Risk-taking behaviour	0.242	0.082	8.714	0.003	1.274	1.085	1.497
Perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 on public transport	-0.305	0.079	14.941	<0.001	0.737	0.631	0.860
Perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 in private car	0.376	0.085	19.688	<0.001	1.457	1.234	1.720
Risk group (ref.: no)	0.228	0.209	1.185	0.276	1.256	0.833	1.893
Contact with risk group (ref.: no)	-0.247	0.166	2.201	0.138	0.781	0.564	1.082
Coronavirus test (ref.: no)	-0.033	0.174	0.035	0.851	0.968	0.687	1.362
Positive test (ref.: no)	-0.155	0.317	0.238	0.625	0.857	0.460	1.595
Quarantine or Isolation (ref.: no)	0.132	0.217	0.370	0.543	1.141	0.746	1.745
Someone in close environment has tested positive (ref.: no)	0.021	0.252	0.007	0.935	1.021	0.623	1.674
Gender (ref.: female)	-0.261	0.165	2.496	0.114	0.770	0.557	1.065
Age (Year)	0.009	0.006	2.149	0.143	1.009	0.997	1.021
Educational level							
Grammar school (ref.: Compulsory and vocational)	-0.119	0.312	0.145	0.703	0.888	0.482	1.636
Higher education (ref.: Compulsory and vocational)	-0.192	0.216	0.789	0.374	0.825	0.540	1.261
Tertiary education (ref.: Compulsory and vocational)	0.130	0.196	0.439	0.508	1.139	0.775	1.673

Note. n = 718 (listwise).

mode.

The perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 on public transport has a negative effect on the probability of choosing the collective instead of the individual travel mode. For a one-unit increase in the perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 on public transport, the odds of choosing the collective travel mode over the individual mode decrease by 26.3 % (B = -0.305, p < 0.001, 95 % CI 0.631 to 0.860).

The perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 in the individual travel mode has a positive effect on the probability of choosing the collective instead of the individual travel mode. For a one-unit increase in the perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 in private cars, the odds of choosing the collective travel mode over the individual travel mode increases by 45.7 % (B = 0.376, p < 0.001, 95 % CI 1.234 to 1.720).

Socio-economic and demographic factors and other risk-related factors are non-significant.

5. Discussion

During a pandemic, tourism travel is affected by governmental regulations and tourist decision-making processes. Governmental regulations, such as travel bans, vaccination passports or enforced quarantine serve as environmental conditions for tourists' travel choices (Hüsler and Ohnmacht, 2023). Tourists respond by altering their destinations and mode of transport choices. Within transportation studies, there is an abundance of research on the impacts of the pandemic on people's everyday travel behaviour (see Hintermann et al., 2023 for peak-time

analysis). However, studies on the influence of health-risk perceptions associated with contracting the coronavirus on tourists' intentions to choose travel modes during the pandemic are still scarce.

Based on the HBM and data from Switzerland, the present study contributes to this research area. We assume that intentions to choose the collective travel mode over the individual one is a function of the perceived susceptibility to, and perceived severity of, the coronavirus and the perceived barriers of applying NPIs against the virus while travelling. Our findings show that the increase of perceived susceptibility has a negative effect on tourists' intentions to choose the collective travel mode over the individual. Specifically, our findings indicate that if the perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 on a mode of transport is high, this supports the alternative. This is the case for both modes of transport, be it individual or collective. If the perceived risk of contracting COVID-19 in a car is high, collective modes are preferred. This may be explained by individuals sharing a confined space that can increase the virus's circulation. Moreover, it is not a statutory obligation to wear a face mask in a car.

Conversely, tourists' perceptions of the risks of contracting the virus on public transport have a negative impact on their intentions to choose the collective travel mode over the individual.

Strong reductions in public transport use during a pandemic are an economical threat to public transport companies, and can have long-term effects. We have seen in Switzerland that it took until 2024 for public transportation to recover. Thus, within collective modes of transport transmission of the virus during a pandemic need to be reduced. It is vital for public transport operators and airlines to improve hygiene by imposing both voluntary and compulsory measures. Through regular sanitation and by reducing occupancy numbers, companies should provide the necessary facilities such as hand sanitiser at bus or train stations, bus stops, and airports, as well as in vehicles. Public transport operators may also make (FFP2-) mask-wearing mandatory. For aeroplanes, airlines can require all passengers to provide negative tests and health declarations. These measures can reduce the risk of contracting (and spreading) the virus, thus lessening the perceived susceptibility, which in turn may increase the use of collective travel modes during the pandemic. These risk-mitigation measures can help public transport operators and airlines prepare for a future pandemic.

We also found that a general risk-taking predisposition (a personal trait) has a stronger effect than susceptibility or preferring collective to individual modes. The risk-tolerant group preferred the collective travel mode for getting to tourist/holiday destinations, in comparison to the risk-averse group. In their study of tourists' preventative travel behaviour during the pandemic, Hüsser et al. (2023) showed that the risk-tolerant exhibited low intentions to apply NPIs while travelling. Studying the characteristics of non-adopters of NPIs, Pedron et al. (2023) and Lang et al. (2021) both reported that this group tended to be more likely male and young. We therefore recommend that destinations targeting adventurous outdoor youth tourist segments should collaborate with airlines and public transport operators in educating passengers about the science behind NPIs and their effectiveness in preventing the spread of the virus. Tourism destination managers may customise their communication programs for this specific tourist group.

Belonging to a risk group, having contact with a risk group, taking a coronavirus test, having a positive test, adhering to quarantine and isolation measures, and exposure to infectious environments, were all found to have no statistical effects on tourists' intentions to choose the collective travel mode over the individual.

We also found no statistical effects of sociodemographic factors (age, gender, and education) on tourists' intentions to choose the collective travel mode over the individual. In their study conducted in India, Bhaduri et al. (2020) also found no effect of age on mode choice of daily travel. However, studying travel mode choices for daily commuting during the COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan, Abdullah et al. (2021) found that those who were male and who had attained higher educational levels were less likely to use the public transport mode over the

individual travel mode. The reason for this difference may lie in the study design. Our study focusses on intentions to choose a particular travel mode for a holiday, while Abdullah et al.'s study investigated self-reported choices of travel mode for the daily commute.

6. Limitations

This present study has some limitations. It does not consider the effects of former travel behaviour, i.e., frequent users of public transport. Rahimi et al.'s (2021) study reported a statistically significant difference of frequent bus use on individuals' choice of travel modes during the pandemic. We had no data on mobility tools such as driving licenses, access to cars and their availability, or holders of public transport season passes (yearly, monthly, weekly). Access to these mobility tools may influence the circumstances in which public transport was preferred to individual travel modes such as private cars, even during a pandemic.

Conclusion

The fear of contracting COVID-19 has become strongly linked to the use of public transportation and can be seen as a stressor for travellers (see Tsoi and Loo, 2023 for commuters). Thus, micro-management strategies of public transport operators are needed to limit the spread of diseases. The lessons learnt from COVID-19 thus may affect future outbreaks. The acceptance and right application of NPIs by tourists is of special importance, as tourism transport contributes to the spread of disease due to cross-border travel. Various measures may reduce anxiety and stress levels about being infected with COVID-19 on public transportation (Tsoi and Loo, 2023). To alleviate transportation stress during COVID-19, Tsoi and Loo (2023, p. 12) rank the top five measures that would improve the transit experience. These include hygienic standards (in train compartments and at stations), better ventilation, compulsory requirements on mask-wearing, social distancing measures and temperature screening of passengers by staff. Additionally, Ohnmacht et al., (2022, p. 11) suggested the following five field of actions for intervention strategies: regulatory and control instruments (including digital infrastructures); ease-of-use interventions (through services and assistance); declarative knowledge (information campaigns); normative persuasive role models; and low-cost interventions (free masks, free testing).

Based on such measures, the confidence of tourists on collective travel modes increases by reduced perceived susceptibility. High compliance with measures reduces the spread of tourist-created disease. In relation to this research, our contribution to science is that tourists' perception of susceptibility, and their general risk-taking predisposition, serves as a further dimension that can add to stress perception regarding collective travel modes. This leads to our contribution for practice to address those perceptions and traveller groups to reduce the swap of shares from collective modes of travel to individual ones during a pandemic. The proper and fast introduction of such measures is needed to flank new waves of infections.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vu Thi Thao: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Andreas Philippe Hüsser:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Timo Ohnmacht:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Timo Ohnmacht reports financial support was provided by Swiss

National Science Foundation (SNSF). If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) within the framework of the National Research Programme “COVID-19” (NRP 78) Grant-N° 407840_4078P0_198336. There is no potential competing interest among the authors.

References

- Aaditya, B., Rahul, T.M., 2021. Psychological impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on the mode choice behaviour: A hybrid choice modelling approach. *Transp. Policy* 108, 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2021.05.003>.
- Abdullah, M., Dias, C., Muley, D., Shahin, M., 2020. Exploring the impacts of COVID-19 on travel behavior and mode preferences. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 8, 100255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2020.100255>.
- Abdullah, M., Ali, N., Javid, M.A., Dias, C., Campisi, T., 2021. Public transport versus solo travel mode choices during the COVID-19 pandemic: Self-reported evidence from a developing country. *Transp. Eng.* 5, 100078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.treng.2021.100078>.
- Abraham, V., Bremser, K., Carreno, M., Crowley-Cyr, L., Moreno, M., 2021. Exploring the consequences of COVID-19 on tourist behaviors: perceived travel risk, animosity and intentions to travel. *Tour. Rev.* 76, 701–717. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-07-2020-0344>.
- Airak, S., Sukor, N.S.A., Rahman, N.A., 2023. Travel behaviour changes and risk perception during COVID-19: A case study of Malaysia. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 18, 100784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2023.100784>.
- Aloi, A., Alonso, B., Benavente, J., Cordera, R., Echániz, E., González, F., Ladisa, C., Lezama-Romanelli, R., López-Parra, A., Mazzei, V., Perrucci, L., Prieto-Quintana, D., Rodríguez, A., Sañudo, R., 2020. Effects of the COVID-19 Lockdown on Urban Mobility: Empirical Evidence from the City of Santander (Spain). *Sustainability* 12, 3870. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093870>.
- Anwari, N., Tawkir Ahmed, M., Rakibul Islam, M., Hadiuzzaman, M., Amin, S., 2021. Exploring the travel behavior changes caused by the COVID-19 crisis: A case study for a developing country. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100334>.
- Bae, S.Y., Chang, P.-J., 2021. The effect of coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19) risk perception on behavioural intention towards ‘untact’ tourism in South Korea during the first wave of the pandemic. *Curr. Issues Tour.* 24, 1017–1035. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2020.1798895>.
- Barbieri, D.M., Lou, B., Passavanti, M., Hui, C., Hoff, I., Lessa, D.A., Sikka, G., Chang, K., Gupta, A., Fang, K., Banerjee, A., Maharaj, B., Lam, L., Ghasemi, N., Naik, B., Wang, F., Mirhosseini, A.F., Naseri, S., Liu, Z., Qiao, Y., Tucker, A., Wijayaratna, K., Peprah, P., Adomako, S., Yu, L., Goswami, S., Chen, H., Shu, B., Hessami, A., Abbas, M., Agarwal, N., Rashidi, T.H., 2021. Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on mobility in ten countries and associated perceived risk for all transport modes. *PLoS One* 16, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0245886>.
- Bartlett, M.S., 1950. Tests of significance in factor analysis. *Br. J. Stat. Psychol.* 3, 77–85. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8317.1950.tb00285.x>.
- Benita, F., 2021. Human mobility behavior in COVID-19: A systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 70, 102916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.102916>.
- Bhaduri, E., Manoj, B.S., Wadud, Z., Goswami, A.K., Choudhury, C.F., 2020. Modelling the effects of COVID-19 on travel mode choice behaviour in India. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 8, 100273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2020.100273>.
- Champion, V.L., Skinner, C., 2008. The health belief model. In: Glanz, K., Rimer, B.K., Viswanath, W. (Eds.), *Health Behavior and Health Education: Theory, Research, and Practice*. Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, pp. 41–62.
- Chua, B.L., Al-Ansi, A., Lee, M.J., Han, H., 2021. Impact of health risk perception on avoidance of international travel in the wake of a pandemic. *Curr. Issues Tour.* 24, 985–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2020.1829570>.
- Cipolletta, S., Andregretti, G., Mioni, G., 2022. Risk Perception towards COVID-19: A Systematic Review and Qualitative Synthesis. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 19, 4649. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19084649>.
- Dingil, A.E., Esztergár-Kiss, D., 2021. The Influence of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Mobility Patterns: The First Wave’s Results. *Transp. Lett.* 13, 434–446. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2021.1901011>.
- Dryhurst, S., Schneider, C.R., Kerr, J., Freeman, A.L.J., Recchia, G., van der Bles, A.M., Spiegelhalter, D., van der Linden, S., 2020. Risk perceptions of COVID-19 around the world. *J. Risk Res.* 23, 994–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2020.1758193>.
- Eisenmann, C., Nobis, C., Kolarova, V., Lenz, B., Winkler, C., 2021. Transport mode use during the COVID-19 lockdown period in Germany: The car became more important, public transport lost ground. *Transp. Policy* 103, 60–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2021.01.012>.
- FSO, 2021a. Educational attainment by sex and age group.
- FSO, 2021b. Population size and change in Switzerland in 2020: definitive figures.
- Germani, A., Buratta, L., Delvecchio, E., Mazzeschi, C., 2020. Emerging Adults and COVID-19: The Role of Individualism-Collectivism on Perceived Risks and Psychological Maladjustment. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17, 3497. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17103497>.
- Golets, A., Farias, J., Pilati, R., Costa, H., 2021. COVID-19 pandemic and tourism: The impact of health risk perception and intolerance of uncertainty on travel intentions. *Curr. Psychol.* 13, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02282-6>.
- He, S., Chen, S., Kong, L., Liu, W., 2021. Analysis of Risk Perceptions and Related Factors Concerning COVID-19 Epidemic in Chongqing, China. *J. Community Health* 46, 278–285. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10900-020-00870-4>.
- Hintermann, B., Schoeman, B., Molloy, J., Schatzmann, T., Tchervenkov, C., Axhausen, K.W., 2023. The impact of COVID-19 on mobility choices in Switzerland. *Transp. Res. Part A Policy Pract.* 169, 103582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2023.103582>.
- Hüsler, A.P., Ohnmacht, T., 2023. A comparative study of eight COVID-19 protective measures and their impact on Swiss tourists’ travel intentions. *Tour. Manag.* 97, 104734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2023.104734>.
- Hüsler, A.P., Ohnmacht, T., Thao, V.T., 2023. Tourists’ preventive travel behaviour during COVID-19: the mediating role of attitudes towards the intention to apply non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) while travelling. *Curr. Issues Tour.* 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2022.2162373>.
- Jenelius, E., Cebecauer, M., 2020. Impacts of COVID-19 on public transport ridership in Sweden: Analysis of ticket validations, sales and passenger counts. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 8, 100242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2020.100242>.
- Jonas, A., Mansfeld, Y., Paz, S., Potasman, I., 2011. Determinants of Health Risk Perception Among Low-risk-taking Tourists Travelling to Developing Countries. *J. Travel Res.* 50, 87–99. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287509355323>.
- Kadali, B.R., Gadiraju, S.S., Gaddam, H.K., 2022. Analysis of Travelers’ Risk Perceptions About Public Transit Systems During COVID-19 Pandemic. *Transp. Res. Rec. J. Transp. Res. Board* 036119812210933. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981221093332>.
- Kaiser, H.F., 1974. An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika* 39, 31–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02291575>.
- Kamenidou, I. (Eirini), Stavrianea, A., Liava, C., 2020. Achieving a Covid-19 Free Country: Citizens Preventive Measures and Communication Pathways. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 17, 4633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134633>.
- Kim, M.H., Lee, J., Gim, T.H.T., 2021. How did travel mode choices change according to Coronavirus Disease 2019? Lessons from Seoul, South Korea. *Int. J. Urban Sci.* 25, 437–454. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12265934.2021.1951823>.
- Lang, R., Atabati, O., Oxoby, R.J., Mourali, M., Shaffer, B., Sheikh, H., Fullerton, M.M., Tang, T., Leigh, J.P., Manns, B.J., Marshall, D.A., Ivers, N.M., Ratzan, S.C., Hu, J., Benham, J.L., 2021. Characterization of non-adopters of COVID-19 non-pharmaceutical interventions through a national cross-sectional survey to assess attitudes and behaviours. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 21751. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-01279-2>.
- Molloy, J., Schatzmann, T., Schoeman, B., Tchervenkov, C., Hintermann, B., Axhausen, K.W., 2021. Observed impacts of the Covid-19 first wave on travel behaviour in Switzerland based on a large GPS panel. *Transp. Policy* 104, 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2021.01.009>.
- Muley, D., Shahin, M., Dias, C., Abdullah, M., 2020. Role of Transport during Outbreak of Infectious Diseases: Evidence from the Past. *Sustainability* 12, 7367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12187367>.
- Nambulee, W., Champahom, T., Jomnonkwo, S., Watthanaklang, D., Ratanavaraha, V., 2023. Comprehending travel intentions during and after the covid-19 pandemic based on psychological theory models. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 22, 100933. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2023.100933>.
- Neuburger, L., Egger, R., 2021. Travel risk perception and travel behaviour during the COVID-19 pandemic 2020: a case study of the DACH region. *Curr. Issues Tour.* 24, 1003–1016. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2020.1803807>.
- Nunnally, J., Bernstein, I., 1994. *Psychometric theory*, 3rd ed. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Ohnmacht, T., Balthasar, N., 2023. Facts & Figures zur touristischen Mobilität in der Schweiz: Definition und erste Ergebnisse [Facts & Figures on tourism transport in Switzerland: Definition and preliminary results].
- Ohnmacht, T., Hüsler, A.P., Thao, V.T., 2022. Pointers to Interventions for Promoting COVID-19 Protective Measures in Tourism: A Modelling Approach Using Domain-Specific Risk-Taking Scale, Theory of Planned Behaviour, and Health Belief Model. *Front. Psychol.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.940090>.
- Ozbilen, B., Slagle, K.M., Akar, G., 2021. Perceived risk of infection while traveling during the COVID-19 pandemic: Insights from Columbus, OH. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 10, 100326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100326>.
- Pappas, N., 2021. COVID19: Holiday intentions during a pandemic. *Tour. Manag.* 84, 104287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2021.104287>.
- Paul, T., Chakraborty, R., Anwari, N., 2022. Impact of COVID-19 on daily travel behaviour: a literature review. *Transp. Saf. Environ.* 4. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tse/tdac013>.
- Pedron, S., Laxy, M., Radon, K., Le Gleut, R., Castelletti, N., Noller, J.M.G., Diefenbach, M.N., Höltscher, M., Leidl, R., Schwettmann, L., Forster, F., Bakuli, A., Eckstein, J., Froeschl, G., Geisenberger, O., Geldmacher, C., Heiber, A., Hoffmann, L., Huber, K., Metaxa, D., Pletschette, M., Rothe, C., Schunk, M., Wallrauch, C., Zimmer, T., Pritsch, M., Wieser, A., Olbrich, L., Thiel, V., Riess, F., Kroidl, I., Saathoff, E., Prückner, S., Zeggini, E., Fuchs, C., Hasenauer, J., Theis, F., 2023. Socioeconomic and risk-related drivers of compliance with measures to prevent SARS-CoV-2 infection: evidence from the Munich-based KoCo19 study. *BMC Public Health* 23, 860. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15759-9>.

- Peralvo, F.C., Vanegas, P.C., Avila-Ordóñez, E., 2022. A systematic review of COVID-19 transport policies and mitigation strategies around the globe. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 15, 100653 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100653>.
- Politis, I., Georgiadis, G., Papadopoulos, E., Fyrogenis, I., Nikolaidou, A., Kopsacheilis, A., Sdoukopoulos, A., Verani, E., 2021. COVID-19 lockdown measures and travel behavior: The case of Thessaloniki, Greece. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 10, 100345 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100345>.
- Rahimi, E., Shabanpour, R., Shamshiripour, A., (Kouros) Mohammadian, A., 2021. Perceived risk of using shared mobility services during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Transp. Res. Part F Traffic Psychol. Behav.* 81, 271–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2021.06.012>.
- Rosenstock, I.M., 1974. Historical Origins of the Health Belief Model. *Heal. Educ. Behav.* 2, 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019817400200403>.
- Scorrano, M., Danielis, R., 2021. Active mobility in an Italian city: Mode choice determinants and attitudes before and during the Covid-19 emergency. *Res. Transp. Econ.* 86, 101031 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2021.101031>.
- Shahin, M.A.H., Hussien, R.M., 2020. Risk perception regarding the COVID-19 outbreak among the general population: a comparative Middle East survey. *Middle East Curr. Psychiatry* 27, 71. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43045-020-00080-7>.
- Shamshiripour, A., Rahimi, E., Shabanpour, R., Mohammadian (Kouros), A., 2020. How is COVID-19 reshaping activity-travel behavior? Evidence from a comprehensive survey in Chicago. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 7, 100216 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2020.100216>.
- Sträuli, L., Tuvikene, T., Weicker, T., Kęblowski, W., Sgibnev, W., Timko, P., Finbom, M., 2022. Beyond fear and abandonment: Public transport resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 16 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100711>.
- Thao, V.T., Hüsser, A.P., Ohnmacht, T., 2022. A combined theory-based explanatory model for predicting tourists' travel intentions during the COVID-19 pandemic: the role of individual's assessment of the compliance with non-pharmaceutical interventions. *Discov. Psychol.* 2 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44202-022-00046-2>.
- The Federal Council, 2020. Coronavirus: Bundesrat erklärt die «ausserordentliche Lage» und verschärft die Massnahmen [Coronavirus: The Federal Council declares the “extraordinary situation” and tightened the measures].
- Tsoi, K.H., Loo, B.P.Y., 2023. A people-environment framework in evaluating transport stress among rail commuters. *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.* 121, 103833 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2023.103833>.
- Unwto, 2020. *UN Tourism Policy Brief Visuals*. World Tour, Organ.
- Wang, J., Guo, C., Wu, X., Li, P., 2022. Influencing factors for public risk perception of COVID-19 –perspective of the pandemic whole life cycle. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 67, 102693 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102693>.
- Weber, E.U., Blais, A.-R., Betz, N.E., 2002. A domain-specific risk-attitude scale: measuring risk perceptions and risk behaviors. *J. Behav. Decis. Mak.* 15, 263–290. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdm.414>.
- Weiber, R., Mühlhaus, D., 2014. *Strukturgleichungsmodellierung. Eine anwendungsorientierte Einführung in die Kausalanalyse mit Hilfe von AMOS, SmartPLS und SPSS [Structural Equation Modeling. An application-oriented introduction to causal analysis using AMOS, SmartPLS and SPSS]*, Springer-Lehrbuch. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-35012-2>.
- WTTC, 2022. *Economic Impact: Global Trends 2022*.
- Zafri, N.M., Khan, A., Jamal, S., Alam, B.M., 2022. Risk perceptions of COVID-19 transmission in different travel modes. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 13, 100548 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100548>.